

ANTIOXIDANT AND HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITIES OF ETHYL ACETATE LEAF EXTRACT OF
Icacinia trichantha ON PARACETAMOL-INDUCED LIVER DAMAGE IN RATS.

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ABSTRACT

Studies were conducted on the *in vitro* anti-oxidant and *in vivo* hepatoprotective effects of ethyl acetate extract of *Icacinia trichantha* leaves. Mature Wistar rats weighing 150-200 g were used to study the changes in alanine aminotransaminase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), bilirubin and protein on paracetamol-induced liver damage in rats. *In vitro* anti-oxidant assays carried out include 1, 1-Diphenyl-2-Picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Assays. Results showed that *I. trichantha* leaf extract at the dose of 400 mg/kg was able to reverse paracetamol induced hepatic damage better than silymarin (P<0.05). It also had positive anti-oxidant activities which were not favorably comparable to that of ascorbic acid (standard drug).

KEYWORDS: Hepatoprotective, anti-oxidant, DPPH, FRAP, *Icacinia trichantha*, liver damage,

INTRODUCTION

Icacinia trichantha is a shrub found in forest and jungle vegetation in Southern Nigeria that grows to about 2 metres and with large tuber. It is called ji muo and unumbe by the Igbos and gbegbe by the Yorubas. Though the root is reported edible, a strong presence of alkaloid has been reported in it as well as benzophenones. The leaf contains a trace only of these compounds. The fruit is a drupe about 2½ cm long with a soft sweet outer pulp which is edible. Igbo people consider the plant to be aphrodisiac, and they use it on soft tumours (Burkill, 1985). Some studies conducted on *I. trichantha* tubers showed that it has purgative activity and potentiated pentobarbital-induced loss of righting reflex (Asuzu and Ugwueze, 1990). The leaves have also been shown to have hypoglycaemic effect on Alloxan-induced diabetic mice (Ezeigbo, 2010). It is now generally accepted that oxidative stress plays a major role in the pathogenesis of diabetes mellitus (Kalavainam *et al*, 2006). This study seeks to determine the protective effect of the leaves of *I. trichantha* on paracetamol induced liver damage as well as its *in vitro* anti-oxidant effect.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and extraction of plant material

Fresh leaves of *Icacinia trichantha* were collected from Nsukka in Enugu State, Nigeria and identified by Mr Ozioko (of the International Centre for Ethnomedicine and Drug Development, Nsukka.). Voucher samples were deposited in the herbarium for reference. The leaves were dried at room temperature and pulverized. Starting plant material was 1.2 kg. This was extracted by cold maceration using absolute ethyl acetate for 48 hours. The filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 40°C to yield 15.25 % of solid residue. This was stored in refrigerator at 4°C for further use.

Experimental animals.

Wistar rats (150-200 g) of both sexes procured from the animal farm of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, were used for the experiment. They were kept under standard environmental conditions of temperature, relative humidity, dark/light cycle, and were fed with standardized pellets and tap water *ad libitum* during the quarantine period. Ethical guidelines in animal handling and use were adhered to Strictly in the execution of the study.

Acute Toxicity Test.

20 Wistar rats, divided into 4 groups of 5 rats per group were used for acute toxicity test. The extract was given *per os* at doses of 250, 500, 1000 and 2000 mg/kg respectively and the animals were subsequently observed for 48 hours for signs of toxicity and death.

Effect of ethyl acetate leaf extract of *Icacinia trichantha* on paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity in rats.

36 Wistar rats weighing 150-200 g of both sexes were used for the experiment. They were divided into six groups of six rats per group. Group 1 received distilled water for 14 days and served as normal control (no challenge with paracetamol). All other groups were challenged with a single dose of 2000 mg/kg of paracetamol, *per os*. Group 2 received paracetamol only (negative control). Group 3 received Silymarin (25 mg/kg) for 14 days. Group 4, 5, and 6 received 75, 150 and 300 mg/kg of the ethyl acetate leaf extract of *Icacinia trichantha* respectively for 7 days. Treatment was initiated 12 hours after the challenge with paracetamol. The collection of blood samples for biochemical studies was through the lacrimal vein of the rats into marked sample bottles. These were allowed to stand for 45 minutes at room temperature. The serum was separated using a Pasteur pipette into sterile serum sample tubes from where they were drawn for biochemical assays. The method of Reithman and Frankel (1957) was adopted for the alanine aminotransaminase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) assays. Alkaline phosphatase activity (ALP) was estimated using the method of King and King (1954). Bilirubin was determined using the method of Malloy *et al.* (1937) as modified by Tietz (1996). Total protein was estimated using the method of Johnson (1943).

In vitro antioxidant assays

1,1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) Antioxidant Assay

The method of Mensor *et al.* (2001) was adopted. 2 ml of test extract at concentrations ranging from 100 µg/ml to 400 µg/ml was each mixed with 1 ml of 0.5 mM DPPH (in methanol). Absorbance at 517 nm was taken after 30 minutes incubation in the dark at room temperature. The concentrations were prepared in triplicates. The percentage antioxidant activity was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ antioxidant activity [AA]} = 100 - \frac{(\text{absorbance of sample} - \text{absorbance of blank}) * 100}{\text{Absorbance of control}}$$

1 ml of methanol plus 2 ml of the extract was used as blank while 1ml of 0.5 mM DPPH solution plus 2 ml of methanol was used as control. Ascorbic acid was used as reference standard.

Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Assay

This was done using the method described by Benzie and Strain (1999). 100 µl of Plasma is mixed with 3 ml of working FRAP reagent (Acetate buffer 300 mM, TPTZ (2, 4, 6-tripyridyl-s- triazine) 10 mM in 40mM HCl and FeCl₃. 6H₂O) and absorbance (593 nm) is measured at 0 minute after vortexing. Thereafter, samples of test extracts at concentrations of 10, 50, 100, 200 and 400 µg/ml were placed at 37°C in water bath and absorption is again measured after 4 minutes. Ascorbic acid standards (100µM-1000µM) were processed in the same way.

Results were calculated as follows.

FRAP value of Sample (µM) = (Change in absorbance of sample from 0 to 4 minute / Change in absorbance of standard from 0 to 4 minute) X FRAP value of standard (1000 µM).

Data Analysis.

Data obtained were presented as mean ± SEM and analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and post-hoc comparisons were carried out using Dunnett's *t*-test. Values of *p*<0.05 were considered significant in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Acute toxicity test:

No signs of toxicity and death were noticed among all the groups of wistar rats. The ethyl acetate extract of *Icacinia trichantha* had no adverse effects on rats up to the dose of 2000 mg/kg. This shows that it is relatively safe and corroborates its use in traditional medicine especially as a remedy for hyperglycemia (Ezeigbo, 2010). *Icacinia trichantha* has promising hepatoprotective effect on the liver damage due to administration of a high dose of paracetamol which causes liver damage (Table 1). Paracetamol (2000 mg/kg) significantly (*P*<0.05) caused increases in all the liver enzymes, bilirubin as well as protein in the rats compared with those given only distilled water. Administration of Silymarin, a powerful anti-oxidant reversed this effect. However, administration of the ethyl acetate extract of *Icacinia trichantha* at the different doses caused a reversal of all the increases in the liver enzymes, bilirubin as well as protein that are comparable to the effect of silymarin. However, *Icacinia trichantha* at 300 mg/kg had even better results than silymarin, causing further decreases in these parameters than were obtained for treatment with silymarin (Table 1). The mechanism of action of the test

extract could be to aid the liver in repairing injured cells and generating new ones. Hence, *I. trichantha* may be useful in reversing hepatic injury caused by strong toxins ad in cases of hepatic cirrhosis.

Table 1: EFFECTS OF THE ETHYL ACETATE LEAF EXTRACT OF *Ichacinia trichantha* ON SERUM AST, ALT, ALP, TOTAL BILIRUBIN AND TOTAL PROTEIN OF PARACETAMOL-INDUCED LIVER DAMAGE IN RATS

DOSE(mg/kg)	AST(IU/L)	ALT(IU/L)	ALP(IU/L)	TOTAL BILIRUBIN (mg/dL)	TOTAL PROTEIN(mg/dL)
Distilled water	37.60±1.29 ^a	67.40±4.82 ^a	64.60±1.96 ^a	0.19±0.04 ^a	7.01±0.15 ^a
Paracetamol(PCM) only	142.00±4.51 ^d	260.60±15.12 ^d	211.00±7.77 ^c	2.11±0.08 ^d	3.99±0.25 ^d
PCM + Silymarin(35mg/kg)	56.25±2.29 ^b	119.75±4.21 ^b	90.75±4.55 ^b	0.15±0.02 ^b	5.99±0.19 ^b
PCM +extract(75mg/kg)	64.00±6.18 ^b	141.40±3.22 ^b	83.75±5.45 ^b	1.54±0.32 ^b	7.02±0.35 ^a
PCM + extract(150mg/kg)	75.40±3.80 ^c	148.26±9.43 ^c	82.80±3.51 ^b	1.57±0.32 ^b	5.66±0.87 ^b
PCM + extract(300mg/kg)	57.99±1.98 ^b	118.007±6.4 ^b	79.23±1.52 ^b	1.29±0.32 ^a	5.51±0.48 ^b

^{abcd} Different superscripts in a row indicates significant difference between the treatment means at the level of probability: p < 0.05

Results of the in vitro antioxidant assay using 1, 1- diphenyl-picryl-hydrazyl radical (DPPH) showed some level of anti-oxidation which is more pronounced at the concentration of 400 µg/ml of the extract. The anti-oxidant effect of the test extract is however, less than that of standard (ascorbic acid) at all the concentrations of the extract. DPPH (Figure 1) is widely used to test the ability of compounds to act as free radical scavengers or hydrogen donors and to evaluate anti-oxidant activity. The DPPH test (Wagner, 1996) provided information on the reactivity of test compounds. Because of its odd electron, 1, 1- diphenyl-picryl-hydrazyl radical (DPPH) gives a strong absorption band at 517nm in visible spectroscopy (deep violet colour). As the electron becomes paired off in the presence of a free radical scavenger, the absorption vanishes, thus the resulting decolorization is stoichiometric with respect to the number of electrons taken up. The scavenging properties of anti-oxidants are often associated with their ability to form stable radicals.

Figure 1: 1,1-Diphenyl-2-Picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) Antioxidant Assay

The results of the FRAP assay shows that ethyl acetate extract of *I. trichantha* has in vitro anti-oxidant effects with all the test concentrations, but showed more anti-oxidant effect at the 400 µg/ml. The method described measures the ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP). At low pH, when a ferric-Trotripyridyltriazine (Fe³⁺ TPTZ) complex is reduced to the ferrous (Fe²⁺ form, an intense blue color with an absorption maximum at 593 nm develops. The reaction is nonspecific, and any half-reaction which has a less-positive redox potential, under reaction conditions other than the Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺TPTZ half-reaction will drive Fe³⁺-TPTZ reduction. Test conditions favor reduction of the complex and, thereby, colour development, provided that a reductant (anti-oxidant) is present. In the FRAP assay, excess Fe³⁺ is used, and the rate-limiting factor of Fe²⁺-TPTZ, and hence color, formation is the reducing ability of the sample (Benzie and Strain, 1999). The in vitro anti-oxidant effects of *I*

trichantha may be an important aspect of its hypoglycaemic effect (Ezeigbo, 2010) as oxidation has been widely accepted to be a major aspect of pathogenesis in diabetes mellitus.

Figure 2 :Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Assay

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